

Multispecies Ovary Tissue Histology Electronic Repository (MOTHER) Slide Scanning Protocol

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I. Overview

Follow these instructions to create a digital image of a complete tissue section on a histology slide. Get started in this order:

1. Log in to the computer and start the Olympus cellSens software.
2. Enter your microscope use start time in the Microscope Log (see binder next to the computer).
3. Turn on the microscope and follow the instructions to scan slides.
4. When done:
 - a. Turn off the microscope and enter your end-time in the Microscope Log.
 - b. Log out of the computer. It will automatically go into “sleep” mode, so you do not need to turn it off.

II. Computer Set-Up

1. The computer should be in “sleep” mode, and you can wake it up by tapping a key on the keyboard.
 - a. If the computer is off, push the power button at the front of the CPU to turn it on.
 - b. If the monitor is off, the power button is under the bottom right-hand corner of the monitor (it’s the first button from the right)
2. Log in with your ASURITE ID and password. If your ASURITE ID doesn't allow you to log in to the computer, try “asuad\ASURITE ID”
3. To save image files directly to Dropbox, make sure the Dropbox App is installed.
4. Double-click on the cellSens Entry icon to open the imaging software.

III. First-Time User Guidelines

1. Make sure the Dropbox App is installed to save image files directly to Dropbox.
 - a. To access a shared Dropbox folder, you must “add” the folder (a team Dropbox folder would have been shared by Dr. Watanabe with you). Look for it under “Shared” and click on “add” to add it to your Dropbox.
 - b. Save all cellSens *.vsi folders and image files (*.ome.tif) to a designated Team Dropbox folder for the species you are scanning.
2. Make sure to log your progress in the appropriate workflow log (see section IV).

IV. Workflow Logs

Workflow logs are Excel workbooks that track a slide through the scanning, follicle ID, and counting process. Each project has its own workflow log in the folder where scanned slides will be saved.

1. To find the respective project workflow log
 - a. Open Dropbox (ASU) app
 - b. Open the file
“ASU_OvaryHistology/ASU_ **PROJECT** _OvaryHistology/**PROJECT** _WorkflowLog.xlsx”
2. If it isn’t already filled in, fill out the Donor Information, columns A through F
3. After scanning your slide, fill columns G through J (refer to section X for more details).

V. CX 33 Microscope Settings

Refer to Figure 1 to see where the numbers in parentheses are on the microscope.

1. Set the main switch (1) to ON and adjust the brightness using the light regulator (3).
2. If needed, rotate the light path selection knob (4) to select the light path for observing the tissue specimen with the eyepieces (5) or on the computer monitor through the camera (6).
3. Place a slide on the stage (2) such that any text on the slide can be read by you (i.e., it is not upside down when you are in front of the microscope. If the text on the slide label faces one of the shorter edges of the slide, place the slide on the stage with the label on the left side.
4. Move the slide and position the desired tissue section under the 4x microscope lens using stage knobs (7). Start with the first tissue section on the left side of the slide (this is section "a").

Figure 1: CX 33 microscope with important parts numbered.

5. Always start with the 4x objective lens and bring the tissue into focus. Adjust the brightness of the field using the light regulator (3) as needed.
 - a. Use the coarse focusing knob (9) first.
 - b. Then use the fine focusing knob (10).
6. To view the tissue at higher magnification, rotate the microscope lens (8). For scanning macaque slides, 10x is the standard magnification, but for small tissue sections, this may be increased to a higher magnification with permission from Dr. Watanabe.

VI. Scanning Histology Slides with cellSens Entry Software Overview

1. Before scanning a tissue section with cellSens Entry, go over the entire tissue section at the magnification that you will be using to check for folds, tears, and/or blurry spots.
 - a. The first section from the left (section "a") should be scanned unless it has folds, tears, or blurry spots (see Figure 2).
 - b. If section "a" is unsuitable, then look at the other sections on the slide; from left to right, they would be labeled "a", "b", "c", "d" etc.

- c. If there are two or more distinct rows of tissue present, start from the leftmost section on the top row and label from left to right, then move to the second row (left to right).
2. Find the best tissue section to scan. **If none of the sections on a slide are suitable** for scanning, make a note in the appropriate Workflow Log (Slide Scanning Notes column), and do NOT scan the slide. Make sure to change the slide number font to **red** in the Workflow Log and add a brief set of notes.

Figure 2: Ovary tissue sections that are suitable for scanning (left), and a section with a fold (right).

3. Go to cellSens software to obtain a digital image. See detailed instructions below (section VII) for using cellSens Entry to scan a slide.
4. When you are done scanning a slide, lower the stage and remove the slide.
5. **Turn the main switch (1) to OFF before leaving the microscope room and sign-out of the Microscope Log.**

VII. cellSens Entry Settings for Scanning Histology Slides

1. Put the light path selection knob on the camera site (shown here and #4 in Figure 1).

2. Open cellSens Entry software if it isn't already open. Shown on the right is an icon for the software, which you should see on the computer Desktop.

3. Click "Camera Control" as shown here

4. Click
5. Under "Exposure", click "Automatic"

6. Adjust the brightness of the field using the light regulator. Setting it around 1 should work so that the exposure is between 1 and 2 ms.

7. Exposure should be between 1 and 2 ms, for resolution of 2052x1086 (High sensitivity) as shown here for both Live/Movie and Snapshot/Process. After making adjustments, click on "Manual" under "Exposure" and double check that the exposure is < 2 ms.

8. Select the correct magnification in cellSens. For example, if you are scanning slides at 10x magnification, choose 10x in cellSens Entry (see image below). This impacts whether the image scale bar will be sized correctly.

9. Click “Process Manager”,

a. then click the Instant MIA icon

b. Under “Instant MIA” select “Overwrite pixels”.

(Note: Prior to 4/19/22 we scanned slides in “Overwrite pixels” then between 4/19/22 and 9/23/22 we used “Overwrite blocks”.)

10. Before scanning the slide, name the image files and set the location where they will be saved.

a. Click “Acquisition Settings”

b. Click Acquisition→Instant MIA→select background color. Confirm that the Default resolution is set at 2052 x 1086 (High sensitivity).

11. Under “Document Name”, click “**Process manager**”

a. Type the slide name in “Text” using the following file naming convention:

AnimalID_XX_SlidenumberSlidesection

- i. AnimalID will be a number at the top of each slide.
- ii. XX indicates the left or right ovary. Use “LT” for left or “RT” for right. If this information is not provided on the slide use “UN” in the file name
- iii. Slide number is located on the lower right corner of the white space on the slide and should be a value between 1 and 300 formatted as “nnn” (e.g., 010 for the number 10, or 002 for slide number 2). **If you encounter a slide with different numbering, ask Dr. Watanabe or one of the graduate students how to proceed.**
- iv. Slides section indicates which section (when multiple tissue sections are available) was scanned. The first section from the left (section “a”) should be scanned unless it is damaged (Refer to **section VI** for more information on how to label and choose the best slide section).
- v. Example of a filename for a scanned image of the third section on the slide below would be, “25065_LT_010c”.

- vi. **Exceptions to this naming convention** for fetal ovaries (e.g., gestational day (GD or G) 130). For Dr. Zelinski’s lab, fetal ovaries are labeled with the mother’s animal ID and possibly G 130 as shown on the slide below, though not always. *We will need to do a quality control check with the metadata provided.*

- 1) The **AnimalID in the workflow log** should be created as “mom’sAnimalID-F#- YY”.
- 2) For the example slide, we know from an email exchange with Dr. Zelinski, that the slide corresponds to the 2nd fetus from mom 20478 on July 2012. Mom’s animal ID is 20478; # = 2 (2nd fetus), YY are the last two digits of the year (=12). Thus, the animal ID in the workflow log reads, “20478-F2-12”.
- 3) The scanned slide image OME tif file name will be, “20478-F2-12_LT_050a.ome.tif”

vii. **Slide File Naming Convention for Collaborator Slides**

“CI_GS_ID_SlideNumber_SectionLetter”

- 1) CI stands for collaborator initials. This is the principal investigator of the team providing the slide.
- 2) GS stands for the genus and species of the animal donor’s scientific name.
- 3) ID is the slide ID that can be found on the slide (If you have questions about this ask Dr. Watanabe).
- 4) SlideNumber: Slide number or letter can be found along with the slide ID written on the slide label.
- 5) Example: Scanning the first (left-most) tissue section on a slide provided by Dr. Kelly Young. Scientific name: “*Semicossyphus Pulcher*”. Slide label: “CSULB 14 477 Extra 1 477”

i. **KY_SP_CSULB14_477**

- b. The first scan for an animal should have Counter start at “0”, and Counter digits = “2”.

Acquisition Settings

- [-] Acquisition
- [-] Document Name
 - [...] Snapshot
 - [...] Movie
 - [...] Process Manager
- [-] Saving
 - [...] Snapshot
 - [...] Movie
 - [...] Process Manager
- [-] Camera

Preview: 21252_RT_005a_00

Customize Text: 21252_RT_005a

Counter start: 0 Counter digits: 2

Reset automatically

All Options...

Default Apply to All

12. Click “Saving” → “Process Manager” → choose the folder where the image should be saved. For example, Dropbox/ASU_OvaryHistology/ASU_[SpeciesName]_OvaryHistology for “Path”

- a. If the animalID has been created, click on the animalID folder.
- b. If you cannot find the animalID folder, then click on “create a new folder” as circled in red below and name the new folder with the “animalID” so the vsi image will automatically save to that folder.

13. After all adjustments in Acquisition Settings have been made, click “OK”
14. Click the “Start” button to begin scanning.
15. When done, click on the “Stop” button.

VIII. Exporting the Image as an ome.tif File

1. Click “File” → “Export to OME” → under “Export to folder”
2. Choose the folder with the same name as the vsi image. For example, Dropbox(ASU)/ASU_OvaryHistology/ASU_[SpeciesName]_OvaryHistology/"Your AnimalID folder"/"AnimalID_XX_SlidenumberSlidersection_xx".
 - a. If the vsi file name is, “21252_RT_002a_00”, then there is a folder with the same name that contains support files for the vsi image. Select this folder, then click “OK”.

A. Rename and Move an Exported ome.tif file

1. Follow the instructions below, if your computer didn't give you an error message, such as "Saving of process results failed". If you get an error message, go to section IX. After you have saved the vsi file:

- i. Open the Dropbox (ASU) app.
- ii. Open the folder ASU_[speciesName]_OvaryHistology, such as "ASU_Macaque_OvaryHistology"
- iii. Open the AnimalID folder.
- iv. Open the MIA.ome.tif folder inside the folder where you saved the exported image,
"_AnimalID_XX_SlidenumberSlidesection_##_/_AnimalID_XX_SlidenumberSlide
section_##_/MIA.ome.tif"
- v. You will see your tif image named as "MIA_1Z_1T.ome.tif"
- vi. Rename the tif image as "AnimalID_XX_SlidenumberSlidesection.ome"
- vii. Cut and paste the tif file "AnimalID_XX_SlidenumberSlidesection.ome.tif" into the main AnimalID folder. For example,
ASU_Macaque_OvaryHistology/AnimalID

IX. Troubleshooting Note for Problems with Saving Images

After scanning the slide, if the computer gives you an error saying the vsi image couldn't save, then do the following:

1. Click "File"
2. Then click "Save As..."
3. Rename the "File name" as "AnimalID_XX_SlidenumberSlidesection" and click "Dropbox(ASU)/ASU_OvaryHistology/ASU_[SpeciesName]_OvaryHistology/" "Your AnimalID folder"
4. Click "Save"

X. Workflow Log Entry After Scanning

1. After scanning a slide, enter information into a workflow log that corresponds to the slide collection.
 - a. Fill out columns G through J.
 - b. And after renaming the tif file, fill out columns K and L.
2. Let your partner do the quality control of your scanned image.
 - a. If the tif image is not completely scanned or it is blurry, please rescan the section (*Refer to rescanning section of protocol for more details*).
 - b. If the tif image is good, then your partner should view the image and fill out the QC columns in the spreadsheet, columns M and N.
3. Relocate the tif file as described above in section VIII (Exporting the Image as an ome.tif File), then fill out column O.
4. If you have any issues during the process, fill out column P with a brief description of what happened. Include the date and your ASURITE ID with the note.

XI. Procedure for Correcting Slide Image Names

Upon discovery of an incorrectly named file:

1. Change the AnimalID font color to red (to stop further processing of the image)
2. Add a note in the “Error Log” column explaining the error or if detailed notes are in the Slide Scanning Notes, reference those.
3. Explain the steps needed to correct the error.
 - a. Renaming a file: You must change the name on ALL of the following files
 - i. *.vsi file
 - ii. The corresponding data folder for the vsi file
 - iii. The ome.tif file if it has been created.
 - iv. Check that the renamed image is clear by opening the vsi file in cellSens. If it isn’t clear, check that “frame.t.0.ets” in the “Stack 1” folder was downloaded from Dropbox onto the computer.

XII. Rescanning a Slide

A slide should be rescanned if the initial scan did not pass quality control check and a better image can be produced whether by rescanning the same slide section or a different section on the same slide.

A. Rescanning the same slide section as the original

1. If you are rescanning the same slide tissue section as the original scan, then the vsi file name counter should be increased by one.
For example, if the original scan was “21252_RT_002a_00.vsi”, then the rescan should be named “21252_RT_002a_01.vsi”. Note that the ome.tif filename should not have the vsi counter values (e.g., “00”, “01”, etc.).

B. Scanning a different section on the slide

1. If you are scanning a different section on the same slide, then start the vsi file counter from “00”.
For example, if the original scan “21252_RT_002a_00.vsi” did not pass the quality control check and you decide to scan section b for the second scan then the rescan should be named “21252_RT_002b_00.vsi”

C. If a scanned image fails a QC check and there is no other section on the slide suitable for scanning

1. Change the font color of the ome.tif file name and the slide number to red and strikethrough ome.tif file name.
2. Strikethrough the location of ome.tif file entry in column O.
3. Write a note in the Slide Scanning Notes (column P) including your ASURITE ID and the date.

After rescanning update the respective workflow log. **Strikethrough** existing text. **Do not delete any existing information from the workflow log.**

1. Enter the corresponding information in Columns K (vsi file name) and L (ome.tif name)
2. Strikethrough columns M (QC check) and N (QC date text). Another QC check will need to be done for the new image.
3. Check that the ome.tif location is correct in column O
4. Enter a brief note in the “Slide Scanning Notes” (column P) documenting that you rescanned the slide and include your ASURITE ID and date.

XIII. Tips for Obtaining Best Quality Images

1. Bring the tissue into focus at 10x, then increase the magnification to 40x and use the fine focus knob to improve the focus if needed, then go back to 10x magnification. The tissue should still be in focus at 10x without any adjustment.
2. When selecting background color make sure to point your selection dropper to the farthest corner of the background. This will prevent the background being darker than the slide section.
3. To avoid tiling effects in your final scanned image, scan from top to bottom then moving to the side and going bottom to top. Continue doing this until you have scanned the whole section.

XIV. Acknowledgements

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